

ACTIVITIES OF EDUCATION AND PRESS WORKERS DURING WORLD WAR II

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Annotation. This article focuses on the history of the activities of education and press workers in Uzbekistan during the Second World War in 1941-1945. It also provides scientific evidence that representatives of this sector actively participated in training new personnel, strengthening the spiritual and educational immunity of the people, and that mass propaganda work carried out through radio, theater, and literature was an important means of convincing the people of victory and inspiring heroism at the front.

Key words: Press, education, higher education, public education, institute, radio, theater, newspaper, magazine, reading room, literary critic, library, university, extramural department, faculty.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola 1941-1945 yillarda ikkinchi jahon urushi davrida O'zbekistonda maorif va matbuot xodimlari faoliyatining tarixiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Shuningdek, bu soha vakillari yangi kadrlar tayyorlash, xalqning ma'naviy-ma'rifiy immunitetini mustahkamlashda faol ishtirok etganligi hamda radio, teatr va adabiyot orqali olib borilgan ommaviy-targ'ibot ishlari xalqni g'alabaga ishontirish, frontdagi qahramonlikka ruhlantirishda muhim vosita bo'lganligini ilmiy asosi keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Matbuot, maorif, oliy ta'lim, xalq ta'lim, institut, radio, teatr, gazeta, jurnal, qiroatxona, adabiyotshunos, kutubxona, universitet, sirtqi bo'lim, fakultet.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается история деятельности работников образования и печати Узбекистана в годы Великой Отечественной войны 1941-1945 годов. Научно доказано также, что представители этой сферы активно участвовали в подготовке новых кадров, укреплении духовно-воспитательного иммунитета народа, а массово-пропагандистская работа, проводимая через радио, театр и литературу, была важным средством убеждения народа в победе и воодушевления на героизм на фронте.

Ключевые слова: Пресса, образование, высшее образование, народное образование, институт, радио, театр, газета, журнал, читальный зал, литературный критик, библиотека, университет, заочное отделение, факультет.

The Second World War was a very difficult and responsible period of testing for Uzbekistan, as for the peoples of the whole world. The war had a serious impact not only in the military sphere, but also in the economic, social, spiritual and educational spheres. During the war years, Uzbekistan became a strong supply base for the front. Industrial enterprises in our country were adapted to the military sphere, all opportunities were mobilized for the front, for victory[1:319]. Even in these difficult circumstances, the education and media sectors in Uzbekistan did not stop their activities, but rather became more active and performed important tasks in inspiring the people to defend their homeland.

Since many teachers were sent to the battlefields, serious problems arose in the education system. In this situation, short-term training courses organized to support the education sector

and eliminate the shortage of teachers became important. By 1943, about 16 thousand new teachers had been trained through these courses. Since most men were mobilized to the front, special attention was paid to the issue of training women as teachers. For this purpose, many higher and secondary specialized pedagogical educational institutions were transformed into specialized educational institutions for women[3:350].

Teachers were active not only in the field of education, but also in public life. In addition to conducting political and moral propaganda among workers, they actively participated in a wide range of initiatives, such as organizing rallies, raising funds for defense funds, preparing gifts for front-line fighters and war veterans, collecting scrap metal, and sponsoring hospitals.

Also, during the war, the teams of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, especially professors, teachers and students, sincerely participated in the interests of the Motherland. In these difficult conditions, many buildings of higher education institutions were converted into temporary hospitals, intended to provide medical care to wounded soldiers at the front. At that time, 29 higher education institutions and 52 secondary specialized educational institutions operated in Uzbekistan. In the autumn of 1941 and early 1942, 31 higher education institutions and 7 military academies were evacuated from the western regions of the Union to Uzbekistan, where their activities continued[4:491].

In 1944, new higher education institutions and specialized faculties were established in Uzbekistan. The Uzbek State University in Samarkand, which had been temporarily closed in 1941, was re-established. Pedagogical institutes were also established in the cities of Chimboy and Urgench, teacher training institutes in Namangan and Margilan, and a theater institute in Tashkent. New faculties were established within the Central Asian State University, such as philology and oriental studies. A natural geography faculty was opened at the Tashkent State Women's Pedagogical Institute, and a cotton processing faculty was established at the Tashkent Textile Institute. At the same time, new faculties were opened at the Central Asian Polytechnic Institute (now Tashkent Technical University), the Tashkent Institute of Agricultural Irrigation and Mechanization Engineers, and a number of other higher education institutions. In addition, in order to expand the education system within sectors and create advanced opportunities for students, a total of 14 higher education institutions opened correspondence departments[5].

The press, which was one of the most important sectors during the war, also became the most effective tool for ideological and political education of the entire population. If we focus on the activities of the press during the Second World War, 200 newspapers were published in Uzbekistan, 124 of which were in the Uzbek language. 52 magazines were also published, 19 of which were in the Uzbek language. The circulation of newspapers published in Uzbekistan amounted to 900 thousand copies, and the circulation of newspapers in the Uzbek language reached 600 thousand copies[2:487]. Newspapers and magazines not only regularly covered the situation at the front, but also covered with journalistic skill the lives of those who were struggling against unprecedented difficulties in the industrial, agricultural, educational, and cultural sectors of the country and working hard to achieve a glorious victory.

A group of writers and journalists from Uzbekistan were sent to various fronts and political administrations to work in front-line newspapers. Among them, Tolkin Rustamov and Rasul Muhammadi worked as instructors in the General Directorate of the Soviet Army, Jalolkhon Azizkhanov, Rustam Abdurakhmonov, Adham Rahmat, Sharif Bulatov, Muhammadjon Murodov, Yulchi Bilolov and others worked as deputy editors in front-line newspapers. Nazir Safarov, Mirzakalon Ismailiy, Zinnat Fatkhullin, Meli Jora, Tolagan Soatov,

Abdulla Sharofutdinov, Adham Hamdam, Tugon Ernazarov and others worked as military correspondents or in other combat areas of the journalistic field[6].

During the war, 14 front-line newspapers and 12 divisional newspapers were published in the Uzbek language. The publication of such newspapers as “Front Haqiqati”, “Kizil Askar Haqiqati”, “Kizil Armiya”, “Vatan Sharafi Uchun”, “Dushmanga Kartsii Olga”, “Sovet Jangchisi” was of great importance. In particular, the newspaper “Sovet Jangchisi” was founded on December 25, 1942 on the South-Western Front and was published until the last days of the war. This newspaper, like other front-line newspapers in the Uzbek language, was published under the slogan “Death to the German invaders!”[3:355]. The newspaper’s pages contained extensive materials about the military-political education of fighters, complex strategies for fighting the evil enemy. Articles telling about the bravery, courage and struggle of Uzbek fighters at the front, as well as texts educating them in the spirit of anger and hatred, were common.

A particularly vivid example of this is the widespread dissemination of letters sent by relatives to the fighters of the Uzbek people. These letters were signed by 2 million 412 thousand people. During the war years, radio workers and cultural and educational institutions also made a great contribution. During this period, 754 cinemas, 11 museums, 360 reading rooms, 1044 clubs, 433 libraries and 28,882 red teahouses became centers for political, cultural and educational work among the masses[2:489].

In conclusion, during the Great Patriotic War of 1941–1945, science, education, and the press of Uzbekistan became one of the spheres of decisive importance for the fate of the country. Even in the difficult conditions of the war, educational institutions did not stop their activities, but actively participated in training new personnel, conducting scientific research, and strengthening the spiritual and educational immunity of the people. The educational system of Uzbekistan, which received evacuated educational institutions and scientists, thereby gave a great impetus to the development of science in our country.

Mass propaganda carried out through the press, radio, theater and literature became an important means of convincing the people of victory, inspiring them to work and heroism at the front. Newspapers and magazines, including front-line publications, became an effective propaganda platform for raising military morale and instilling hatred for the enemy. The activities of national journalists and writers at the front occupy a special place in the history of the national press.

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